

CHARACTERISTICS OF CONTROL OF STARTING MODES IN FUEL AND ENERGY ENTERPRISES

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Abstract

Modern technological systems of oil refining are characterized by a large number of different types of units combined in complex technological connections with each other. In this regard, the solution to the problem of optimal control in large oil refining systems consists not only in finding the optimal modes for each technological block, but also in creating coordination links between the nodes of the technological scheme. There are certain advantages to solving the optimization problem by a complex decomposition method in complex oil refining systems. This approach simplifies the solution of the optimal control problem from a mathematical point of view, and at the same time from the point of view of organizing its solution in the process. Taking into account these features, two approaches are considered for the decomposition of systems with a complex hierarchical structure that interact with each other.

Keywords: technological process, transient processes, oil refining, starting mode, heating of the engine

The most characteristic transient processes that affect the modes of load nodes include processes occurring during starting processes. With the simultaneous start of several engines, commensurate in total power with the power of another system, it can have a significant impact on the starting mode. With sufficient power of the engines to start the process, checking the effect of starting the engines on the system mode must be carried out without fail [1,2].

The start of the engines in motion, or the starting mode of the primary oil refinery, which is part of the total load, is the process of the transition of the engines and, similarly, the working elements from the initial state to the state of rotation at maximum speed. Starting motors is one of the nominal transients. When designing modes and choosing a similar mechanism, it is determined whether a given engine can "turn" (from $w = 0$ to $w = w_0$) the mechanism attached to it, for which:

- determine the engine start time;
- determine how significant the given duration of the start-up process is;
- check the smoothness of the start (which is especially important, for example, for pumping oil);
- estimate the heating of the engine at start-up;
- evaluate the acceleration constant at start, which helps for a number of mechanisms, for example for a lift when carrying.

These issues are resolved when designing start-up modes and therefore are not considered when studying transient processes in the process node, where they are

mainly considered on system tasks, which include determining the significance of starting processes from the standpoint of the admissibility of the normal operation of the primary oil refining system.

Although the start of engines is determined in relation to the basis of "systemic issues", but in order to solve the problems that arise here, it is necessary to study the characteristics of engines and the elements driven by mechanisms [3,4].

During start-up, the engine must reach the torque necessary, firstly, to overcome the moment of resistance of the mechanism, and, secondly, to create a certain kinetic energy of the rotating masses of the unit. The multiplicity of the starting motor in relation to the nominal value is for asynchronous motors: 1.5-2 - with a rheostatic start (for motors with a phase rotor) and 5-8 - when starting a motor with a squirrel-cage rotor.

Starting conditions are usually divided into light, normal and heavy. Under light conditions, the required torque at the beginning of the rotation of the motor is from 10 to 50% of the nominal.

Normal starting conditions include those under which the mechanism requires a starting torque equal to 50-75% of the nominal.

Severe conditions include those under which the required initial torque is from 75 to 100% of the nominal and higher. The latter include the conditions for starting such mechanisms as compressors, crushing drums, various mixing devices, as well as pumps with an open valve and drives with a significant moment of inertia [5,6].

Fig. 1. Scheme of starting the production of sulfuric acid in a furnace
 GP-Hot layered furnace, KU-waste heat boiler, E1 E2- dry electrofilters; P-flame; 1 - air, 2 - fuel gas, 3 - pyrite, 4 - water, 5 - steam, 6 - electrical voltage, 7 - flue gases

G_v - air intake, G_k - pyrite, G_t fuel supplied to the furnace, G_p fuel supplied to the electrostatic precipitators, by changing the flow rate of the fuel gas supplied to the burner of the electrostatic precipitators, as well as the current G_n of the electrodes of the electrostatic precipitators, the start-up process is controlled. These controls are an integral part of the time. The limit of variation of the parameter G_t is determined by the conditions of continuous combustion of fuel in the furnace, and the range of variation of the parameter G_p is determined by the conditions of continuous combustion in the flame of electrostatic precipitators. The permissible limit value for the parameter G_n is determined by the current in the electric field circuit of the filters.

Limiting conditions for operating variables include melting of the inner surface of the furnace lining and the formation of destructive thermal stresses throughout its thickness, condensation of aggressive compounds on the surface of the waste heat boiler and electrostatic precipitator. This follows from the formalization of the requirements, with the exception of the violation of the autothermal process of pyrite combustion. J_0 The efficiency of the vehicle launch process is characterized by the consumption of energy (electricity, fuel gas) and material (water, air, pyrite) resources.

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